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Explicit potentially inappropriate medications criteria for older population in Asian countries: A systematic review

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ABSTRACT

Background: Explicit potentially inappropriate medications (PIM) criteria are commonly used to identify and deprescribe potentially inappropriate prescriptions among older patients. Most of these criteria were developed specifically for the Western population, which might not be applicable in an Asian setting. The current study summarizes the methods and drug lists to identify PIM in older Asian people.

Methods: A systematic review of published and unpublished studies were carried out. Included studies described the development of explicit criteria for PIM use in older adults and provided a list of medications that should be considered inappropriate. PubMed, Medline, EMBASE, Cochrane CENTRAL, CINAHL, PsycINFO, and Scopus searches were conducted. The PIMs were analyzed according to the general conditions, disease-specific conditions, and drug-drug interaction classes. The qualities of the included studies were assessed using a nine-point evaluation tool. The kappa agreement index was used to evaluate the level of agreement between the identified explicit PIM tools.

Results: The search yielded 1206 articles, and 15 studies were included in our analysis. Thirteen criteria were identified in East Asia and two in South Asia. Twelve out of the 15 criteria were developed using the Delphi method. We identified 283 PIMs independent of medical conditions and 465 disease-specific PIMs. Antipsychotics were included in most of the criteria (14/15), followed by tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs) (13/15), antihistamines (13/15), sulfonyleureas (12/15), benzodiazepines (11/15), and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAIDs) (11/15). Only one study fulfilled all the quality components. There was a low kappa agreement ($k = 0.230$) between the included studies.

Conclusion: This review included 15 explicit PIM criteria, which most listed antipsychotics, antidepressants, and antihistamines as potentially inappropriate. Healthcare professionals should exercise more caution when dealing with these medications among older patients. These results may help healthcare professionals in Asian nations to create regional standards for the discontinuation of potentially harmful drugs for elderly patients.

1. Introduction

The global population is aging rapidly. Between 2015 and 2050, the global population of adults over 60 is expected to nearly double, from 12% to 22%.¹ The most tremendous increase will happen in Southeast Asia, with 13.7% of the population predicted to be 60 or older by 2030, rising to 20.3% by 2050.² In many older adults, comorbidities and the number of medications accumulate proportionally with age. This leads to polypharmacy, commonly defined as the use of five or more medications which is associated with adverse health outcomes in older adults.³ It also increases the risk of taking potentially inappropriate medications (PIMs), where the potential dangers outweigh the benefits among older people.⁴ PIMs usage among older adults has been associated with higher risks of hospitalization, mortality, and healthcare costs.^{5,6}

As polypharmacy is a common phenomenon among older adults,

with prevalence ranging between 26% and 86%,⁷⁻⁹ optimizing the medication regimen among older adults is critical. Studies have proposed using explicit and implicit PIM criteria to guide appropriate prescribing to identify PIM among older patients.⁴

Explicit PIM criteria are well-defined statements that focus on PIMs among older persons. The criteria (generally refer to explicit PIM criteria unless otherwise stated) are usually developed based on evidence from clinical trials, experts' opinions, and Delphi methods. One of the most commonly used PIM criteria is the Beers criteria. It was developed in the United States to assist and alert healthcare providers on PIM usage among older individuals in specific clinical conditions.¹⁰ For instance, it recommended the avoidance of benzodiazepines in older people with history of falls or fractures.¹¹ Subsequently, region-specific explicit PIM criteria were developed in different countries, including the STOPP-/START criteria in Ireland,¹² PRISCUS in Germany,¹³ McLeod criteria in Canada,¹⁴ and French Consensus Panel List in France.¹⁵

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Implicit PIM criteria, by contrast, are subjective quality metrics that focus on the patient's condition and needs. As such, it is a patient-centered criteria that is more holistic, sensitive, and comprehensive approach to PIM identification and deprescribing.¹⁶ For example, a commonly used implicit criteria is the medication appropriateness index (MAI).¹⁷ However, using implicit PIM criteria is time-consuming and heavily reliant on the knowledge and experience of healthcare professionals, making the implementation very challenging in daily clinical practice.¹⁶

Implicit criteria have limited applicability outside the research setting as they are time-consuming and challenging to implement. Explicit criteria, on the other hand, are more user-friendly for physicians since they contain clearly defined components, including medication names and specific clinical scenarios. In the past ten years, the implementation of explicit criteria to detect PIMs has become common to reduce polypharmacy and drug-related problems among the older Asian population.^{18–24}

A previous systematic review by Motter and colleagues identified 36 explicit PIM lists, of which six were Asian studies.²⁵ Meanwhile, a Brazilian review included 58 explicit PIM lists, and 13 were Asian PIM criteria.²⁶ However, neither review assessed the included studies' qualities, which is essential to ensure the relevance and reliability of the included studies.^{25,26} Notably, most of the explicit criteria used in the previous studies were based on medications commonly used in Western countries, which may not be applicable in Asian countries due to regional variations in drug formularies and health systems.²⁷ While the previous reviews^{25,26} included some Asian studies, they were not comprehensive, as some studies published in non-English language were excluded. The present review aims to address the gaps in existing literature by systematically reviewing available evidence to summarize the range of tools and medication lists to identify PIM among older persons in Asia.

2. Methods

This systematic review was registered with PROSPERO (CRD42022374732).

2.1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies were included if they: 1) reported on the development of an explicit PIM list of medications that should be avoided; 2) published works in a peer-reviewed journal, unpublished materials in healthcare institutions, universities, and government websites; and 3) were conducted in an Asian country based on World Bank classifications.²⁸ Randomized controlled trials and systematic reviews were excluded. We only considered papers that were published in English or Chinese.

2.2. Search strategy and selection

Seven databases, including PubMed, Medline, EMBASE, Cochrane CENTRAL, CINAHL, PsycINFO, and Scopus, were searched from database inception until October 30, 2022 for eligible studies. The search was performed using the keywords " (Aged OR geriatrics OR elderly) AND (deprescription OR inappropriate prescribing OR deprescribing OR inappropriate medication) AND (Asia)." This was supplemented with a search for the reference list of identified articles. The full search term can be found in [Supplementary Table 8](#).

Retrieved studies were screened by titles and abstracts based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria by two independent reviewers. The full text of articles was retrieved to determine eligibility and inclusion, with discrepancies resolved through a third reviewer.

2.3. Data extraction

Two independent reviewers extracted the data. The following

information was extracted: publication year, nation, setting, participant count, criteria development processes, explicit PIM criteria description, classes of medications listed, and their limitations. The list of medications was then classified based on their medication classes. These were further grouped based upon: i) PIM independent of disease or condition, ii) PIM that should be avoided in specific disease or condition, and iii) drug-drug interactions. To aid the interpretation, we compiled the medications and medication classes based on the ATC/DDD classification.²⁹

2.4. Quality assessment

We assessed the qualities of the included studies using a nine-point Delphi evaluation tool developed by Nasa and colleagues.³⁰ The tool assesses nine aspects, including systematic identification of problem area, selection of panel members, anonymity of panelists, controlled feedback, iterative rounds, consensus criteria, analysis of consensus, closing criteria, and stability of results which were graded on a three-point scale (yes, no, unclear). A score of 1 was given to any component marked "yes" while no mark was given to "no" and "unclear."

2.5. Agreement index

The kappa agreement index was used to evaluate the level of agreement between the identified explicit PIM tools. Kappa values can range between -1.0 and 1.0 , with higher values representing better agreement.³¹

2.6. Data synthesis

Due to the heterogeneity of study designs and outcome measures, results were described narratively following the Synthesis Without Meta-analysis (SWiM) guideline.³²

This study was registered in the Malaysia National Medical Research Registry (RSCH ID-22-05410-YHR).

3. Results

We identified 1206 articles, and after removing duplicates, 772 abstracts and articles were screened for eligibility. Thirty-one articles were finally screened with full text, and 16 were excluded due to the following reasons: articles in languages other than English or Chinese ($n = 2$), did not examine the population of interest ($n = 3$), modeling study ($n = 1$), no explicit PIM criteria listed ($n = 2$), study not conducted in Asia ($n = 8$). The final study included 15 articles ([Fig. 1](#)).

3.1. Characteristics of included studies

The identified studies ($n = 13$) were mainly from East Asia and Pacific, namely South Korea (4 studies), China (2 studies), Japan (2 studies), and one each from Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore, Indonesia, and Thailand. The remaining two were from South Asia, i.e., Pakistan and Sri Lanka ([Table 1](#)).

To develop the PIM criteria, most studies began by reviewing existing literature and previous PIM lists (including Beers, STOPP, PRISCUS, Canadian criteria) and generated a potential list of PIM drugs. For instance, Beers and STOPP criteria were used in the criteria developed in Taiwan, Korea, Pakistan, and Hong Kong.

Subsequently, most studies used Delphi method ($n = 12$) to finalize the PIM criteria through consensus. These included a range of experts, including geriatricians, cardiologists, internal medicine specialists, family medicine specialists, and pharmacists; in some studies, surgeons, neurologists, psychiatrists, and urologists. These studies had conducted at least 2 Delphi rounds, with between 6 and 36 experts.

Three studies did not use Delphi method for validation and

Fig. 1. PRISMA flow diagram illustrating selection of studies.

finalization. Chau et al. (2015) developed the Singapore PIM criteria through in-house expert reviews,³³ while Fauziyah and colleagues contextualized and finalized the Indonesian PIM criteria to their setting through large-scale field testing and validation.³⁴ Kojima et al. (2016) finalized the Japanese-STOPP criteria by soliciting opinions from experts in professional bodies involved in geriatric care and public review.³⁵

3.2. Study quality

The quality assessment found that only the Thai criteria fulfilled all nine tool components. It is crucial that each participant remains anonymous to eliminate biases like group conformity and dominance. The anonymity of individual members in the Delphi rounds was the component that most studies (14/15) did not address clearly. Other components which most frequently absent or not clearly described were the stability of results (9/15), the predetermined number of Delphi rounds before the study ends (closing criteria) (9/15), analysis of consensus (5/15), and consensus criteria (4/15) (Table 2).

3.3. PIM criteria categories

The explicit criteria identified often reported a list of PIM drugs

independent of diagnosis or clinical condition. The 15 studies included a total of 67 medication classes, including 283 medications (Supplementary Table 1), which often listed antipsychotics ($n = 14$), tricyclic antidepressants ($n = 13$), and first-generation antihistamines ($n = 13$) as PIM that should be avoided independent of a person's diagnosis. Other common medication classes were sulfonylureas ($n = 12$), peripheral alpha-1-blockers ($n = 11$), benzodiazepines ($n = 11$), NSAIDs ($n = 11$), antiarrhythmics ($n = 10$) and central alpha-blockers ($n = 10$) (Table 3).

These criteria also included a list of drugs that could potentially interact with specific diseases or drugs and listed a total of 71 conditions covering 67 medication classes and 465 medications (Supplementary Tables 2 and 3). In particular, these studies had commonly listed avoidance of the following medication classes such as NSAIDs in people with chronic kidney disease ($n = 12$), history of gastric ulcers ($n = 11$), heart failures ($n = 10$), and hypertension ($n = 9$). The studies also cautioned on the use of anticholinergics in people with urinary retention or benign prostatic hyperplasia ($n = 10$), glaucoma ($n = 10$), and chronic constipation ($n = 9$). Other commonly reported drugs that should be avoided include the use of antipsychotics in Parkinson's disease ($n = 10$), as well as benzodiazepines ($n = 8$) and tricyclic antidepressants ($n = 7$) in people with a history of falls or fractures (Table 4).

Drug-drug interactions were listed in 8 out of the 15 included PIM criteria. Concurrent use of ACEIs or ARBs with potassium-sparing drugs

Table 1
Characteristics of included studies.

No.	Authors and year of publication	Tools/Criteria	Validation method	Targeted population	Framework of criteria	Limitations
1.	Chang et al. 2019 ⁵³	PIM-Taiwan	Review of Beers 2015 criteria, ¹¹ STOPP version 2, ¹² FORTA, ⁵⁴ Japan PIM list ³⁵ followed by two rounds of modified Delphi by 24 experts	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	Two categories of PIMs: i. General PIMs: 131 individual drugs and 9 drug combinations ii. Disease-specific: 131 individual drugs across 10 medication classes	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included In-house guidelines developed by two pharmacists and vetted by one geriatric consultant. PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
2.	Chau et al. 2015 ³³	STOPP-START Singapore NUH In-house Guidelines	Review of STOPP-START criteria version 2 ¹²	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	89 criteria, including 55 STOPP (9 classes) and 34 START criteria (9 classes).	In-house guidelines developed by two pharmacists and vetted by one geriatric consultant. PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
3.	Fauziyah et al. 2020 ³⁴	STOPP-Indonesia	Forward-backward translation of STOPP version 2 ¹² by 5 translators, followed by review by STOPP authors, expert committee (8 experts), pre-testing (n = 34), and field test (n = 230). Content validity, face validity, and internal consistency were assessed and deemed satisfactory.	Not stated	81 PIM criteria grouped into 13 sections: indications of drugs, cardiovascular system, coagulation system, central nervous system, renal system, gastrointestinal system, respiratory system, musculoskeletal system, urogenital system, endocrine system, medication will high fall risk, analgesic, and antimuscarinic/anticholinergic.	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
4.	Jun et al. 2022 ⁴⁶	PIM-Korea 2022	Systematic review and identification of 22 PIM tools, followed by two-round modified Delphi method by 12 experts and 2 rounds of feasibility tests among 7 pharmacists.	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age staying in long-term care facilities	77 PIM items were divided into 5 sections: PIMs in general (18 items), potential drug interactions (14 items), disease-specific PIMs (26 items), dose adjustment (2 items), and potential omissions (17 items).	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Only applicable to older people in long-term care facilities, excluding end-of-life patients.
5.	Kim et al. 2010 ⁵⁵	PIM-Korea 2010	Review of Beers 1991 criteria, ¹⁰ Canadian, ¹⁴ Zhan's Classification ⁵⁶ followed by two rounds of modified Delphi by 14 experts	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	Two categories of PIMs: i. General: Total 57 PIMs in 3 categories: i. drugs that should be avoided (n = 42), ii. Drugs that should be monitored (n = 13), iii. Drugs with a low level of risk (n = 2) ii. Disease-specific: Total 93 PIMs with 29 diagnoses in 3 categories: i. drugs that should be avoided (n = 63), ii. Drugs that should be monitored (n = 28), iii. Drugs with a low level of risk (n = 3)	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
6.	Kim et al. 2015 ⁵⁷	PIM-Korea 2015	Review of Beers 2012 criteria, ⁵⁸ STOPP version 1, ⁵⁹ PRISCUS criteria ¹³ followed by two rounds of modified Delphi by 20 experts	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	7 classes of medications comprising a total of 26 ingredients	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included Alternatives drugs not included
7.	Kim et al. 2018 ⁶⁰	PIM-Korea 2018	Review of STOPP version 2, ¹² Beers 2015 criteria, ¹¹ PRISCUS, ¹³ Korean PIM list 2010, ⁵⁵ Korean Health Insurance and Review Service, Seoul National University Bundang Hospital PIM criteria, matching with reimbursable drugs database, followed by 4 rounds of Delphi rounds by 14 geriatric specialists.	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	Two categories of PIMs: i. General: 62 drugs irrespective of comorbidities ii. Disease-specific: 48 drugs or drug classes across 18 conditions	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
8.	Kojima et al. 2016 ³⁵	STOPP-Japan	Review of Japanese Guidance Statement on Appropriate Medical Services for the Elderly. ⁶¹ A systematic review of drug treatments for 15 clinical areas, including 2098 articles.	persons aged ≥ 75 years of age	Two categories of drugs: i. Drugs to be prescribed with caution: 19 drug classes ii. Drugs to consider starting: 8 drug classes	The list of drugs was derived from a systematic review, and newer drugs may not be included in the list

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

No.	Authors and year of publication	Tools/Criteria	Validation method	Targeted population	Framework of criteria	Limitations
9.	Mazhar et al. 2018 ¹⁹	PIM-Pakistan	Initial lists were drafted by the authors and sent to 16 professional bodies and the public to review before being finalized. Review of 2015 Beers criteria ¹¹ and STOPP criteria version 2, ¹² followed by 2 rounds of Delphi by 12 specialists in geriatric medicine.	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	32 PIMs consisted of NSAIDs, antihistamines, urological spasmolytics, antiemetics, H2-blockers, cardiovascular agents, antidepressants, and benzodiazepines.	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
10.	Pazan et al. 2020 ⁶²	Japan FORTA	Review of 2018 EURO-FORTA, ⁶³ 2017 OAC-FORTA, ⁶⁴ and 2015 LUTS-FORTA, ⁶⁵ followed by 2 Delphi rounds by 13 experts in geriatric pharmacotherapy.	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	210 PIMs across 24 indications, divided into 4 classes: A & B potentially appropriate; C & D potentially inappropriate.	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
11.	Samaranayake et al. 2019 ⁶⁶	STOPP/START Sri Lanka	Review of STOPP/START criteria version 2, ¹² followed by 2 rounds of Delphi by 6 experts.	Older person (age not specified)	105 criteria, including 70 STOPP (14 classes) and 35 START criteria (9 classes).	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included
12.	Wang et al. 2018 ⁴²	PIM-China	Review of Beers 2015 criteria, ¹¹ Canadian, ¹⁴ Japan, French, ¹⁵ Norwegian, ⁶⁷ PRISCUS, ¹³ Korean, ⁵⁵ Austrian, ⁶⁸ Thai, ⁴⁴ Taiwan PIM criteria ⁵⁹ and severe ADR reports from 22 hospitals followed by 3 rounds of modified Delphi	persons aged ≥ 60 years of age	Two categories of PIMs: i. General: Total 72 PIMs across 13 classes in 2 categories: i. drugs that should be avoided (n = 28), ii. Drugs that should be used with caution (n = 44) ii. Disease-specific: Total 44 PIMs with 27 diagnoses in 2 categories: i. drugs that should be avoided (n = 20), ii. Drugs that should be used with caution (n = 24)	Criteria to detect drug omission not included
13.	Wang et al. 2019 ⁴⁷	High-risk perioperative medications	A systematic review of possible high-risk perioperative medications literature, followed by 2 rounds of Delphi by 36 experts.	Older person (age not specified)	86 high-risk medications across 13 medications classes, among 120 conditions	Limited to perioperative medications
14.	Winit et al. 2008 ⁴⁴	High-risk medication-Thai	Literature reviews of elderly PIM use and adverse drug reaction using handbooks and databases, followed by 3 rounds of Delphi survey by 17 experts.	Older patients (age not stated)	77 practice statements divided into 3 sections: i. medications with potential adverse reactions (n = 33), ii. drug-disease interactions (n = 32), iii. drug-drug interactions (n = 12).	Criteria to detect drug omission not included Alternatives drugs not included
15.	Zhang et al. 2021 ⁷⁰	PIM-Hong Kong	Review of French, ¹⁵ Canadian, ¹⁴ Thai, ⁴⁴ Norwegian, ⁶⁷ PRISCUS, ¹³ STOPP version 2, ¹² and Beers 2015 criteria ¹¹ followed by two rounds of modified Delphi by 8 experts	persons aged ≥ 65 years of age	Two categories of PIMs: i. General: 77 PIMs independent of diagnosis ii. Disease-specific: 87 PIMs with specific medical conditions	PIMs were developed using pre-existing standards, and evidence from current clinical trials was not thoroughly examined. Criteria to detect drug omission not included

without monitoring of serum potassium (n = 4), aspirin with warfarin (n = 4), aspirin with clopidogrel (n = 4), NSAIDs with warfarin (n = 4) were the most common drug-drug interactions. Meanwhile, three PIM criteria are recommended against using two or more drugs with antimuscarinic or anticholinergic properties (Table 5, Supplementary Table 4).

Other components listed in the PIM criteria include special consideration of use and alternative therapies (Supplementary Table 5). For example, the criteria recommended the short-term use (for less than three months) of NSAIDs with proton-pump inhibitors (PPIs) and long-term use of paracetamol. These lists also recommended the maximum duration of usage for classes of medications, such as benzodiazepines (for less than four weeks) and PPIs (for less than eight weeks) (Supplementary Tables 6 and 7).

The kappa agreement index of the 15 PIM criteria was analyzed

based on the list of PIM drugs (Table 6). The analysis noted that there was only a fair agreement in the total drugs listed among various countries or even within the country (average kappa: 0.230). For instance, the recent list of PIM published in 2022 in Korea fairly agreed with previous versions published in 2010 (k = 0.318), 2015 (k = 0.379), and 2018 (k = 0.249). Meanwhile, the two Chinese indexes published in 2018 and 2019 poorly agreed with each other (k = 0.112). The highest degree of agreement with moderate strength was found between Indonesia vs. Sri Lanka criteria (k = 0.578), Korea 2010 vs. Thai criteria (k = 0.518), and Korea 2010 vs. Hong Kong criteria (k = 0.518) (Table 6).

When analyzed by medication classes, all PIM criteria generally listed first-generation antipsychotics (93.3%), first-generation antihistamines (86.7%), tricyclic antidepressants (86.7%), sulfonyleureas (80.0%), and benzodiazepines (73.3%) as part of their criteria.

Table 2
Quality assessment of included studies.

No.	Authors and years	Systematic identification of problem area	Selection of panel members	Anonymity of panelist	Controlled feedback	Iterative rounds	Consensus criteria	Analysis of consensus	Closing criteria	Stability of results	Scores (X/9)
1.	Chang et al., 2019	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	7
2.	Chau et al., 2015 ^a										
3.	Fauziyah et al., 2020 ^a										
4.	Jun et al., 2022	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	6
5.	Kim et al., 2010	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	7
6.	Kim et al., 2015	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	6
7.	Kim et al., 2018	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	4
8.	Kojima et al., 2016 ^a										
9.	Mazhar et al., 2018	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	3
10.	Pazan et al., 2020	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	6
11.	Samaranayake et al., 2019	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	5
12.	Wang et al., 2018	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	1
13.	Wang et al., 2019	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	7
14.	Winit et al., 2008	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
15.	Zhang et al., 2021	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	7

^a Delphi method was not employed.

However, 22 medication classes only appeared in one out of the 15 criteria (6.7%) (Supplementary Table 1).

4. Discussion

To our best knowledge, this is the first study that compiled the explicit PIM criteria across the Asian region. This review identified 15 PIM criteria from 10 Asian countries which have developed country-specific PIM criteria, outnumbered those included in previous reviews.^{25,26} Studies included in this review listed 283 medications independent of diagnosis and 465 condition-specific medications. A low degree of kappa agreement was observed across the included studies. Most criteria were developed based on previously established PIM criteria and literature but did not consider global or local adverse drug reaction reports.

Our review concurs with previous reviews by Schiavo et al. and Motter et al. which found that most PIM lists were developed using established criteria (e.g., Beers and STOPP criteria) and validated using Delphi methods but with significant differences across different criteria.^{25,26} This is probably because medication management in older adults is highly complex and personalized, with limited evidence base to guide its development due to the heterogeneity of specialties involved. As such, the approaches taken to develop it and the professionals' attitude toward its development varies, which may explain this heterogeneity.

Our analysis found that antipsychotics, tricyclic antidepressants, and antihistamines are among the most common medication classes listed in all identified criteria. This is unsurprising given that the use of antipsychotics is common among older Asian adults with dementia and schizophrenia.^{28,29} For instance, a recent study found that 40.5% of older persons with schizophrenia in 15 Asian nations took two or more antipsychotics concurrently.³⁶ Another review found that nearly one in eight adults in Taiwan was prescribed an antipsychotic.³⁷

Interestingly, our study found that sulfonylureas were also listed as one of the most common medication classes across the Asian PIM criteria. This is possibly due to the popularity of sulfonylurea usage

among physicians, where nearly three in every five individuals with diabetes on an oral hypoglycemic agent was prescribed sulfonylurea.^{38,39} However, its use should be cautioned as they are associated with a higher risk of hypoglycemia, weight gain, fracture risks, and cardiovascular events.^{38,40}

This review revealed that the Asian PIM criteria were mostly developed using a modified Delphi technique involving experts from various specialties. The Delphi technique is a structured method for controlling group communication to enable a group of people to address a complex issue.⁴¹ This technique is instrumental in setting priorities and developing policies, such as a PIM list for this study. Other validation methods could include a comprehensive review validation and an expert committee meeting, followed by field testing.³⁴ However, this method is labor-intensive and time-consuming, therefore not widely used in developing explicit PIM criteria.

Our study also noted an aspect often overlooked by various studies when developing the PIM criteria: the safety profile evaluation of new/novel medications. In our review, only the PIM criteria developed by Wang and colleagues for China considered the adverse drug reaction reports when developing their tool, where they performed literature reviews and identified ten pre-existing PIM criteria complemented with severe ADR reports from 22 hospitals.⁴² Indeed, pharmacovigilance data represents a novel yet important source of information that can provide regional-specific data commonly unavailable in the literature. For instance, the Brunei National Pharmacovigilance Centre identified the risk of fluoroquinolones and denosumab use in older patients,⁴³ which were not commonly included in previous PIM criteria. As such, future studies should also consider analyzing the global and local ADR database to identify and assess the risks of medications in older adults in developing explicit PIM criteria.

The review also found that no new criteria were proposed in all of the Asian PIM criteria lists. This is not surprising since in the Delphi procedure, the aim is to achieve a consensus view across subject matter experts on a research question. More often than not, there is rarely any opportunity for proposing new criteria or comments, which may reflect the lack of new criteria compared to existing PIM criteria such as Beer's

Table 3
PIM independent of diseases across Asian PIM criteria.

No.	Medications classes	ATC Class	Taiwan 2019	Hong Kong 2021	China 2018	Korea 2022	Korea 2015	Korea 2018	Korea 2010	Japan 2016	Japan 2020	Wang 2019	Singapore 2015	Indonesia 2020	Thai 2007	Pakistan 2019	Sri Lanka 2019	Sum
East Asia										South Asia								
1.	Antipsychotics/Neuroleptics (including phenothiazines)	N05	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	14
2.	Tricyclic antidepressants	N06	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		13
3.	First-generation antihistamines	R01/ R05/ R06	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	13
4.	Sulfonylureas	A10	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X			X	X		X	12
5.	Benzodiazepines	N05	X			X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X	X	11
6.	Anti-inflammatory products (NSAIDs)	M01	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X			X	X		11
7.	Peripheral alpha-1 blockers (e.g., prazosin, terazosin, doxazosin)	C02	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X	X			11
8.	Antiarrhythmic (e.g., amiodarone, procainamide)	C01	X	X	X			X	X		X			X		X	X	10
9.	Central alpha-blockers (e.g., clonidine, methyl dopa, reserpine)	C02	X		X				X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	10
10.	Antithrombotic Agents (e.g., clopidogrel, warfarin, aspirin, ticlopidine)	B01			X			X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	8
11.	Propulsives (e.g., metoclopramide)	A03	X			X		X	X	X				X	X	X		8
12.	Urological (e.g., solifenacin, tolterodine, oxybutynin)	G04	X	X	X		X	X	X	X					X			8
13.	Digoxin	C01	X	X	X			X		X		X			X			7
14.	Calcium channel blockers (e.g., verapamil, diltiazem)	C08		X	X	X			X		X				X	X		7
15.	Estrogens (including combination)	G03	X	X		X		X	X					X	X			7
16.	Antispasmodics (belladonna, hyoscine, scopolamine)	A03		X	X	X		X	X			X			X			7
17.	Nonbenzodiazepines hypnotics (e.g., zolpidem)	N05	X	X		X		X		X		X		X				7
18.	Theophylline	R03			X	X						X	X	X	X		X	7
19.	Muscle relaxants (e.g., orphenadrine, phenylbutazone, baclofen)	M03		X	X	X		X	X						X			6
20.	Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRI)	N06	X			X			X	X		X				X		6

Table 4
PIM in specific diseases or conditions across Asian PIM criteria.

No.	Disease	Drug/Drug Classes	Taiwan 2019	Hong Kong 2021	China 2018	Korea 2022	Korea 2010	Korea 2018	Japan 2022	Wang 2019	Thai 2007	Singapore 2015	Indonesia 2020	Pakistan 2019	Sri Lanka 2019	Sum
			East Asia								South Asia					
1.	Chronic kidney disease	All types of NSAIDs	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	12
2.	Delirium, dementia, cognitive impairment	Anticholinergics (e.g., antipsychotics, benzodiazepines, tricyclic antidepressants)	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	11
3.	History of gastric or duodenal ulcers	Non-COX2 selective NSAIDs	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	11
4.	Parkinson's disease	Antipsychotics	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	10
5.	Parkinson's disease	Antiemetics (e.g., metoclopramide)	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	10
6.	Heart failure	NSAIDs	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	10
7.	Chronic constipation	Tricyclic antidepressants									X	X	X	X	X	10
8.	Urinary retention/ benign prostatic hyperplasia	Anticholinergics (e.g., tricyclic antidepressants, neuroleptics)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X	10
9.	Glaucoma	Anticholinergics (e.g., tricyclic antidepressants)		X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	10
10.	Chronic constipation	Anticholinergics (e.g., antihistamines and antispasmodics)		X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	9
11.	Hypertension	NSAIDs		X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	9
12.	History of gastric or duodenal ulcers	Aspirin	X	X			X	X			X	X		X	X	8
13.	Heart failure	Nondihydropyridine calcium channel blockers (e.g., diltiazem/verapamil)	X	X	X		X	X				X	X		X	8
14.	History of falls or fractures	Benzodiazepines	X	X	X	X	X	X				X		X		8
15.	History of falls or fractures	Tricyclic antidepressants		X	X	X	X	X			X			X		7
16.	Heart failure	Thiazolidinediones (e.g., pioglitazone)	X	X	X			X				X	X		X	7
17.	Delirium, dementia, cognitive impairment	Antipsychotics	X	X				X	X			X	X		X	7
18.	Syncope	Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors	X	X	X	X						X	X		X	7
19.	Bronchial asthma	Beta-blocker	X	X		X	X				X	X	X			7
20.	Blood clotting disorder	Antithrombotic agents			X		X	X			X	X	X		X	7

Table 5
Drug-drug interactions across Asian PIM criteria.

No.	Medications classes	Korea 2022	Japan 2022	China 2019	Thai 2007	Singapore 2015	Indonesia 2020	Sri Lanka 2019	Pakistan 2019	Sum
		East Asia						South Asia		
1.	Concurrent use of ACEIs or ARBs with potassium-sparing drugs without monitoring of serum potassium				X	X	X	X		4
2.	Aspirin and warfarin	X			X	X		X		4
3.	Aspirin and clopidogrel	X				X	X	X		4
4.	NSAIDs and warfarin/thrombin inhibitor/Factor Xa inhibitors	X			X		X	X		4
5.	Clopidogrel and warfarin	X				X		X		3
6.	NSAIDs and steroids without PPI prophylaxis	X		X			X			3
7.	NSAIDs and antiplatelet agents without PPI prophylaxis				X		X	X		3
8.	Concomitant use of two or more drugs with antimuscarinic/anticholinergic properties (e.g., bladder antispasmodics, intestinal antispasmodics, TCAs, and first-generation antihistamines)					X	X	X		3
9.	NSAIDs and ACEI/ARBs	X							X	2
10.	warfarin and sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim	X			X					2
11.	Beta-blockers and verapamil							X	X	2
12.	Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors with beta-blockers, digoxin, diltiazem, and verapamil						X			1
13.	NSAIDs and loop diuretics	X								1
14.	ACEI and ARBs	X								1
15.	Warfarin and macrolide or quinolones	X								1
16.	Benzodiazepines and opioids	X								1
17.	Phenytoin and sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim	X								1
18.	NSAIDs and SSRIs	X								1
19.	Concomitant use of two NSAIDs								X	1
20.	NSAIDs and antihypertensives								X	1
21.	Dipyridamole and aspirin		X							1
22.	Cimetidine and CNS drugs (TCA, benzodiazepines, carbamazepine)				X					1
23.	Digoxin and amiodarone				X					1
24.	Digoxin and HCTZ				X					1
25.	Digoxin and loop diuretics				X					1
26.	Digoxin and macrolide antibiotics				X					1
27.	Digoxin and verapamil				X					1
28.	Warfarin and cimetidine/metronidazole				X					1

Table 6
Cohen Kappa agreement matrix across Asian PIM criteria.

	Taiwan 2019	Singapore 2015	Indonesia 2020	Korea 2022	Korea 2010	Korea 2015	Korea 2018	Japan 2016	Pakistan 2018	Japan 2020	Sri Lanka 2019	China 2018	China 2019	Thai 2008	Hong Kong 2021
Taiwan 2019		0.174	0.404	0.480	0.453	0.391	0.453	0.416	0.299	0.174	0.300	0.385	-0.045	0.286	0.416
Singapore 2015	0.174		0.482	0.178	0.239	0.407	0.163	0.095	0.304	-0.081	0.505	0.181	0.056	0.174	0.095
Indonesia 2020	0.404	0.482		0.407	0.310	0.359	0.237	0.106	0.266	0.038	0.578	0.291	0.046	0.329	0.329
Korea 2022	0.480	0.178	0.407		0.318	0.379	0.249	0.202	0.286	0.075	0.248	0.465	0.004	0.341	0.410
Korea 2010	0.453	0.239	0.310	0.318		0.297	0.362	0.196	0.352	0.086	0.208	0.479	-0.083	0.518	0.518
Korea 2015	0.391	0.407	0.359	0.379	0.297		0.371	0.315	0.206	-0.101	0.204	0.287	0.018	0.315	0.315
Korea 2018	0.453	0.163	0.237	0.249	0.362	0.371		0.389	0.136	0.010	0.208	0.417	0.025	0.260	0.389
Japan 2016	0.416	0.095	0.106	0.202	0.196	0.315	0.389		0.152	0.252	0.222	0.200	0.116	0.026	0.221
Pakistan 2018	0.299	0.304	0.266	0.286	0.352	0.206	0.136	0.152		0.164	0.002	0.197	0.060	0.299	0.226
Japan 2020	0.174	-0.081	0.038	0.075	0.086	-0.101	0.010	0.252	0.164		0.109	-0.016	0.022	-0.062	-0.062
Sri Lanka 2019	0.300	0.505	0.578	0.248	0.208	0.204	0.208	0.222	0.002	0.109		0.216	0.080	0.144	0.222
China 2018	0.385	0.181	0.291	0.465	0.479	0.287	0.417	0.200	0.197	-0.016	0.216		0.112	0.508	0.508
China 2019	-0.045	0.056	0.046	0.004	-0.083	0.018	0.025	0.116	0.060	0.022	0.080	0.112		-0.045	0.009
Thai 2008	0.286	0.174	0.329	0.341	0.518	0.315	0.260	0.026	0.299	-0.062	0.144	0.508	-0.045		0.675
Hong Kong 2021	0.416	0.095	0.329	0.410	0.518	0.315	0.389	0.221	0.226	-0.062	0.222	0.508	0.009	0.675	

p<0.001

p<0.01

p<0.05

or STOPP/START.

We assessed the qualities of the included studies which generally employed the Delphi method to construct the PIM criteria. Notably, the quality of these studies varied. For instance, panel members' anonymity, which prevents group conformities towards a vocal Delphi member, was only reported in the Thai PIM criteria.⁴⁴ Other essential components, such as closing criteria and stability of results were also not commonly reported. As such, we strongly recommend that the conduct and report of Delphi studies follow established quality criteria^{30,45} to ensure the rigor, reliability, and validity of Delphi studies and the tools developed using such methods.

Our analysis noted a relatively low overall kappa agreement ($k = 0.23$) across the included PIM criteria, which ranged from low to moderate. For instance, the degree of agreement between the four explicit PIM criteria developed for South Korea ranged between 0.2 and 0.4, suggesting poor agreement between tools. Results are in contrast to another previous study by Schiavo and colleagues, who reported a kappa agreement of 0.72 from 58 PIM tools.²⁶ This could be attributable to the fact that around half of the tools included by Schiavo et al. were constructed using previously published tools and include mostly PIM in general practice.²⁶ In comparison, we included PIM criteria that were developed using hospital adverse drug reactions data⁴² and were targeted at older people staying in long-term care facilities⁴⁶ and perioperative patients,⁴⁷ which may explain the lower agreement in our analysis.

5. Implications

Taken together, it is important to develop PIM lists specific to the Asian context due to the differences in formulary available in each country. In addition, due to genetic differences, certain medications had a higher risk of eliciting adverse responses in different ethnic groups. For instance, Han Chinese populations exhibited a six-fold greater prevalence of the HLA-B*5801 allele than US White populations, putting them at higher risk of severe cutaneous adverse responses caused by allopurinol.⁴⁸ Furthermore, variations in pharmacogenomics, drug metabolism, and toxicity (e.g. clopidogrel, warfarin, phenytoin, tricyclic antidepressants) were detected across different Asian subpopulations,⁴⁹ warranting the use of local pharmacovigilance data in developing PIM criteria. There is also a need to work towards consensus for certain medication classes specific to the Asian context, such as antimuscarinics and anticholinergics, in order to standardize the identification and deprescribing of PIM.

In addition, it may be beneficial to organize and consolidate existing PIM criteria into an electronic repository to keep the PIM list up-to-date and facilitate usage in research and clinical practice. One such exercise was by Ivanova and colleagues, who compiled, analyzed, and constructed a repository with a total of 650 explicit PIM criteria based on the EU7, Beers list, and STOPP/START criteria.⁵⁰ These criteria can be integrated into the electronic patient health information and prescribing system and facilitate the automated detection of PIM during prescribing and medication reconciliation. Combining different PIM criteria in a repository can be useful when ambiguity arises.

6. Strength and limitations

We searched seven databases and unpublished materials, covered most of the PIM criteria in the Asian region, and did not limit the search to English language only. We assessed the qualities of included PIM lists, which were not performed in previous reviews.^{25,26} Nevertheless, there are some limitations to this study. Firstly, while we searched for unpublished studies, we only managed to identify the PIM lists from 10 countries and may have missed those not published online as these may be only distributed internally in the host countries. Secondly, the PIM list only identifies potential drugs for exclusion but not drug omissions. As most attention is currently focused on PIM, this may be essential to

optimize medication management in older adults. Studies to date have suggested that underprescribing medications is widespread and affects more than half of the population despite the benefits of its usage.^{51,52}

7. Conclusion

The current study systematically compiled the medications included in 15 Asian PIM criteria published over the past three decades. Antipsychotics, antidepressants, and antihistamines were identified as the most commonly included medication classes across Asian PIM criteria. Healthcare professionals should be cautious when encountering these medications in older adults. This study revealed the need to review drug safety reports to keep the PIM lists current. These findings could aid healthcare providers in Asian countries in developing local criteria and guiding the deprescribing of potentially inappropriate medications among older adults.

Study registration

This systematic review was registered with PROSPERO (CRD42022374732) and the Malaysia National Medical Research Registry (RSCH ID-22-05410-YHR). Ethics approval was waived by the Medical Research and Ethics Committee as this study did not involve human subjects.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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